

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957781.

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GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER 957781

WP6 - ACCEPT solution integration, pre-validation, roll-out

D6.5 – ACCEPT wrapper prototype

Responsible organisation	CIRCE
Contributing organisation(s)	Hypertech, Mytilineos, EDBR, LaSolar, AEM, Viesgo
Due date of Deliverable	31/07/2022
Actual date of submission	31/08/2022
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public

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Version history

Version	Date	Comments
0.2	26.07.2022	First draft for peer review
0.3	19.08.2022	Second draft for peer review
0.9	13.09.2022	third draft for peer review
0.91	13.09.2022	forth draft for peer review
0.92	22.09.2022	Fifth draft for peer review
1.0	26.09.2022	Final version of submission
1.1	10.01.2022	Corrected typo

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Abbreviations

API	Application Program Interface
DAM	District Assets Manager
DR	Demand Response
DSO	Distribution System Operators
TSO	Transport System Operators

1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and goals

The scope of this deliverable is to present the activities performed in the context of Task 6.3 of the ACCEPT project, regarding the development of the Accept Solution Emulator (ASE) component and its integration into the ACCEPT solution.

The ASE's main function is to enable testing of the solution use cases [1] which require external inputs that do not exist on the current environment. This includes market price signaling and Demand Response (DR) signaling for DR scenarios, which is especially important as DSO /TSO do not have yet the capabilities in place to send signals for DR schemes. The ASE has two main components; one is the Market Emulator which sends market signal including market pricing for the day and at least 24h into the future. The second component is the Market Emulator which emulates the preferences of a DSO and translates them into DR actions.

The main goal of this deliverable is to:

- Describe in detail the capabilities and functionalities of the ASE
- Describe the various scenarios modelled for testing of the solution

1.2. Relation to other tasks and deliverables

The aim of the T6.3 is to help with the demonstration of the solution by providing external inputs not currently available.

The following relations to other task and deliverables are therefore noted:

- T2.1 Market actor & prosumer requirements & business scenario definition

This task covers the use cases of the project and as such is the main source of the functional requirements for the project. DR scenarios and use cases cannot be tested without the ASE

- T2.3 System architecture design, configuration & elaboration

This task covers the architecture of the whole solution including the architecture of the ASE.

- T5.2 District asset management component

This task covers the DAM which is manages district level assets and their participation in DR schemes.

- T5.4 Horizontal supporting engines for the Energy Community Tools

The Energy Community Tools manage community / building DR scheme participation

- T5.5 Vertical tools for energy community roles & user interfaces

This tools cover the virtual power plant that is used to offer ancillary services such as congestion management.

- T6.2 ACCEPT solution integration & testing

This task cover the integration and testing of the solution. The ASE is necessary in order to test the use cases involving market prancing and demand – response schemes

1.3. Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable is divided in the following parts.

The first one presents a general overview of the deliverable, the scope and goals of the ASE and its relation to other task as well as a description of the structure of the deliverable.

The second describes one of the main components of the ASE, the DSO Emulator and explains the rationale behind the scenarios it offers.

The third section describes the other main component of the ASE, the Market Emulator.

The fourth one describes the architecture of the ASE and documents the REST API used to access its functionalities by other components.

2. DSO emulator module

The DSO emulator models the preferences of a DSO for DR schemes. This is particularly important for use cases 8 and 9. To be able to analyze data coming from Viesgo we built a Backoffice consisting of an Elasticsearch database [2] and a Kibana [3] frontend which we used to normalize and visualize data as well as extract customized reports. The graphs we see in the deliverable are extracted from this backend as well as the data used to drive the different scenarios. The backend to analyze the data as well as the implicit and explicit DR services are the three main modules of the emulator.

2.1. Implicit DR scheme

In the implicit DR scheme, the DSO emulator request pricing data for the market emulator. Then the DSO emulator sets up a price markup scheme, in which prices from the market are recalculated applying markups ranging from -20% to 25% of the total price, using data from the expected congestion as a basis. To do this the DSO emulator evaluates the network congestion level (based on the percentiles of the scenarios) and then evaluates whether congestion is going to grow or diminish in the next hour.

For example, let's take scenario 06E7M5C2108050101 (find more information below in section 2.5.3), Tuesdays have maximum congestion at 13:00. 12:00 would be allocated a +15% markup over the original price due to its congestion but is marked with a 10% instead since the following hours are even more congested. 13:00 is the most expensive hour at 25% markup since its both at maximum congestion and congestion is going to diminish in the next hour. Hours with the least congestion will be the cheapest i.e. from 01:00 to 08:00 in this scenario. The DSO emulator also makes energy cheaper in hours prior to a demand increase (use energy now before congestion) and more expensive in hours leading to a demand decrease (wait for demand to decrease) incentivizing a flattening of the demand curve.

2.2. Explicit DR scheme (day ahead)

In the explicit demand scheme, the DSO emulator generates directly power signals for the communities. The core idea is similar to the implicit DR, the DSO request the communities to increase demand in low congestion times and request the community to decrease demand in high congestion events, we assume for this scheme congestion is always due to generation, as is the case for all the modelled scenarios used for it. For this it follows the values in the heatmap of the scenario (see section 2.5, for example figure 4) so when we are in the top percentiles, we try to decrease demand. The amount of the generated power signals for the communities is proportional to the network capacity (in this case we model this by using the historical data values as an indicator of the network capacity). In this case however we take special care in times where demand is leading to a congestion so that even if we are in a high percentile, we might ask for a consumption increase as long as the following hour is even more congested.

At this time, we actively ask for demand increases in low consumption times whether or not there is going to be congestion in order to have a more active role that helps testing, but we plan on making this behavior optional, so we will not give setpoints to the community in times where there is sustained low demand (relative to the network capacity as modelled).

Explicit DR schemes rely on the assumption that there are existing contracts and SLAs to regulate the remuneration of the flexibility services provided by the communities.

2.3. Explicit DR scheme (real time)

Due to the limitations of the data available and its granularity, the scenarios modelled using data from Viesgo assume some ahead planning. To demonstrate closer to real time behaviors we include a flag to set the scenarios to real-time. This transforms the scenario into a stochastic model working in 15-minute intervals.

In this mode demand congestion probability is a function of the demand of the baseline scenario. If we look at the heatmaps for the scenarios (e.g figure 4) each heatmap includes 10 different colors which separate the demand in ten intervals. The intervals are from 0 to 15%, 15% to 25%, 25% to 40%, 40% to 50%, 50% to 60%, 60% to 70%, 70% to 80%, 80% to 90%, from 90 to 95% and from 95% to 100%.

Let's use *ord* as the ordering the percentiles from 1 to 10 from lowest to highest demand.

For a given time period t , considering, ord_t is the percentile of the demand in the interval, the probability of congestion Pc_t is: $Pc_t = (ord_t \div 100)^2 \times 25$

In this case we also introduce a probability of congestion due to excessive generation. We have assigned the probabilities by looking at data from the Spanish generation composition. From November to April each time interval has a probability of $pw_t = 0.05$ and from May to October a probability of $pw_t = 0.01$ which accounts for wind energy production. For solar energy we use the following time periods:

$$\begin{cases} per = 1 \text{ from } 21:00 \text{ to } 08:00 \\ per = 2 \text{ from } 17:00 \text{ to } 20:00 \\ per = 3 \text{ from } 08:00 \text{ to } 11:00 \\ per = 4 \text{ from } 11:00 \text{ to } 17:00 \end{cases}$$

From November to April $ps_t = 0.03$ for periods 3 and 4 and $ps_t = 0.00$ otherwise. From April to October $ps_t = 0.05$ for periods 3 and 4, $ps_t = 0.02$ for period 2 and $ps_t = 0.00$ otherwise.

We add both probabilities $pw_t + ps_t$ to calculate pg_t the probability of congestion due to generation.

Since it makes no sense to have both congestion due to generation and demand at the same time if we have a demand congestion event then we don't calculate the chance of congestion due to generation.

Explicit DR schemes rely on the assumption that there are existing contracts and SLAs to regulate the remuneration of the flexibility services provided by the communities.

2.4. Data from Viesgo

For the DSO emulator data coming from MV to LV substation transformers is used. This data came from the northern Atlantic coast of Spain. More specifically data from the following transformers is used.

Province	Municipality	SCENARIO
LUGO	LUGO(CAPITAL)	SC0827
LUGO	LUGO(CAPITAL)	SC1885
CANTABRIA	SANTANDER	SC0376
LUGO	GUNTIN	SC0828
LUGO	BEGONTE	SC0869
PALENCIA	AGUILAR DE CAMPOO	SC1473
CANTABRIA	PIELAGOS	SC0844
CANTABRIA	CAMARGO	SC0101

An overview of the data as a whole shows that demand peaks in the winter and does not vary a lot depending on the weekday, hourly patterns are not modified depending on seasons despite the demand increase in winter. Peak demands times are from 9:00 to 12:00 and from 20:00 to 23:00.

Figure 1 Heatmap of aggregated energy consumption on a monthly/hourly basis

Figure 2 Heatmap aggregated consumption on a weekly/hourly basis

Figure 3 Distribution of consumption by weekday

We have capitalized on the different patterns of the transformer data to interpret them as different scenarios. Each transformer has its own heatmap with a distinct hourly pattern. Modelled scenarios come from a variety of different networks ranging from rural to urban and from residential to commercial areas. We can see in the graphs for each scenario how demand curves change for each scenario.

For now, seasonal differences have not been taken into account, the idea was to create scenarios where we could demonstrate demand response as an ancillary service to reduce congestion and seasonal differences mean there would be entire months without congestion, so it was decided to model only weekday variations since seasonal variations did not have a great impact in weekly energy flows.

This means that at any given time, when queried about its preferences the DSO emulator will take into account the day of the week and the hour but will not change its preferences depending on the month we are in.

We use the percentile scale shown in the images as a guide for the DSO preferences. In reality although most of these networks have high energy traffic, they do not have real technical problems (it is very rare for a network in Spain not to be oversized). However, for the sake of representing network congestion in the DSO emulator we are going to work under the assumption that any time in which percentile 95th of network demand is reached the network is actually congested. We also assume that network capacity is in line with the demand of each scenario so network capacity of a scenario will be in line with its peak demand.

2.5. Modelled scenarios

2.5.1. SC0827 (Lugo)

This scenario, available for use in the DSO emulator, has only one consumer, a big building dedicated to public services. We include a table with a description of the consumers

Consumers	description
1	Public services

Demand is heavily clustered around weekdays and around business hours, we include a heatmap showing the distribution of the energy demand which drives the preferences of the DSO emulator for this scenario.

Figure 4 Weekday / hourly heatmap of energy consumption for SC0827

We can use this scenario to demonstrate behaviors in urban areas with big commercial spaces.

2.5.2. SC1885 (Lugo)

This scenario, available for use in the DSO emulator, has several commercial services which work during the night. We include a table with a description of the consumers.

Consumers	description
2	Utilities (waterworks)
3	Construction
2	Wholesale commercial services
1	Hospitality sector
4	Public administration activities
1	Radio station
1	Gambling establishment
1	Others
65	Households

Demand is heavily clustered around nighttime. We include a heatmap showing the distribution of the energy demand, which drives the preferences of the DSO emulator for this scenario.

Figure 5 Weekday / hourly heatmap of energy consumption for SC1885

We can use this scenario to demonstrate behaviors in urban areas with nighttime activities.

2.5.3. SC0378 (Santander)

This scenario, available for use in the DSO emulator, has a mix of households and commercial buildings as we can see in the following table.

Consumers	description
7	Wholesale commercial services
8	Transport and storage services
1	Offices
3	Education, Sporting facilities & Health services
8	Other services
305	Households

In this scenario we can spot high levels of congestion from 11:00 to 14:00 hours and also congestion around 22:00 hours. On the other hand, demand from 01:00 to 08:00 is very low. We include a heatmap showing the distribution of the energy demand, which drives the preferences of the DSO emulator for this scenario.

Figure 6 Weekday / hourly heatmap of energy consumption for SC0378

We can use this scenario to demonstrate behavior in mixed urban areas.

2.5.4. SC0828 (Guntin)

This scenario, available for use in the DSO emulator, is mostly rural households and some public administration sites as we show in the following table.

Consumers	description
1	Utilities (waterworks)
4	public administration offices
39	Households

Demand peaks around 22:00 every day. There is more demand on weekends probably due to it mostly being households. We include a heatmap showing the distribution of the energy demand, which drives the preferences of the DSO emulator for this scenario.

Figure 7 Weekday / hourly heatmap of energy consumption for SC0828

We can use this scenario to demonstrate behavior in rural / suburban households with little non residential activity.

2.5.5. SC0869 (Bengonte)

Rural, some farms and public facilities. We can see the consumers in the following table:

Consumers	description
1	Primary sector activities
3	Utilities (waterworks)
1	Primary school
1	Sporting facilities
1	public administration offices
39	Households

Looking at the heatmap for the energy consumption we can see more demand on around 22:00 and also increased demand on weekends particularly from 12:00 to 14:00.

Figure 8 Weekday / hourly heatmap of energy consumption for SC0869

We can use this scenario to demonstrate behavior in rural areas with some economic activity.

2.5.6. SC1473 (Aguilar del campo)

Rural area, some manufacturing and farms well as households as we can see on the following table:

Consumers	description
2	Primary sector activities
1	Manufacturing
2	Others
1	public administration offices
45	Households

Demand is much smaller on weekends. Clustered around business hours and peaking on Mondays and Tuesdays.

Figure 9 Weekday / hourly heatmap of energy consumption for SC1473

We can use this scenario to demonstrate communities with manufacturing activities nearby.

2.5.7. SC0844 (Pielagos)

As we can see on the following table this scenario has lots of commercial services combined with households

Consumers	description
15	Wholesale and retail commerce
3	Construction
8	Transport services
10	Hospitality sector
2	Communication services
2	Law and accounting
1	Gambling establishment
11	Others (Commercial activities)
208	Households

Looking at the heatmap demand peaks from 13:00 to 14:00 but is high from 09:00 to 22:00. Demand in the night hours is less than half of peak demand.

Figure 10 Weekday / hourly heatmap of energy consumption for SC0844

This scenario allows testing of dense, mixed commercial and household districts.

2.5.8. SC0101 (Carmargo)

This scenario is dominated by the consumption of a manufacturing plant as we can see in the table.

Consumers	description
1	manufacturing
1	Others

Demand is always high but is greater from 10:00 to 19:00 and much lower during weekends.

Figure 11 Weekday / hourly heatmap of energy consumption for SC0101

This scenario can allow us to test environments dominated by manufacturing activities.

3. Market emulator module

The market emulator module serves the purpose of having a readily available price source for the project components including the ASE which needs these prices for the implicit DR scenario (use case 9). Pricing from the Market emulator is also used in use cases 4 and 11. Prices from the market emulator component will also be considered by the Retailer tool of the energy community when forming the energy tariffs for the prosumers within their portfolio.

The market emulator by default gives current (24h ahead) prices which is what we use for the implicit DR scenario elaboration but can also answer queries for past prices (up to 2018) which enables us to simulate scenarios with different conditions.

To be able to produce the default 24h ahead prices the market emulator uses both real data and a prediction module which forecasts prices to complete the 24h ahead data.

3.1. Data sources

3.1.1. OMIE [4] Repository of electricity prices (for Spain and Portugal)

Prices of electricity of Spain and Portugal are available since 2017. Each day OMIE publishes market prices for the next day at 14:00 pm (Madrid time). We have downloaded all historical data into a local repository which we update daily. We use this data to do price prediction to work on the day ahead scenarios. We can also use it simulate behaviors based on past data, the ASE accepts request with a date (into the past) and will return DSO preferences and market pricing based on that data.

Figure 12 Energy prices historical data for the Spanish market

3.1.2. ESIOS [5]: Repository of energy generation indicators

The range of indicators available vary from solar photovoltaic energy and fossil oil to biomass and geothermal/oceanic.

We collected this data as it might be relevant to the evolution of the prices. The extracted data offers an interesting visualization of the evolution of the energy mix. However not all the indicators have the same availability. In general, they will become available before 8 o'clock AM, but apart from the time when they become eligible to be downloaded, not all the indicators have all their time slots filled with usable values.

We studied using these indicators to enhance price forecasting but discarded the usage due to gaps in data and poor relevance in price forecasting. These indicators could be used together with other external inputs in order to predict the future composition of the energy mix, most importantly the percentage of energy coming from renewable sources which looking at the data might be a more relevant variable in the evolution of energy prices, but the calculation of this prediction was deemed out of scope for the market emulator.

Figure 13 Energy composition indicators for the Spanish energy market

3.2. Price forecast

In order to complete the 24h ahead price signal we have made a prediction module based on machine learning using the data from the prices and the weather. At 14:00 on a given day makes an hourly 24h prediction of day +2. This means that for example at 14:00 14/09/2022 we get from OMIE prices for 15/09/2022 and we calculate the 24h hourly prices for 16/09/2022. We have gotten a mean absolute percentage (MAPE) error of about 15% and a R² (determination coefficient) of 0,395.

To assess the quality of the prediction and give us an overview of the market emulator we built a Backoffice UI to help us detect gaps in data and gauge the accuracy of the prediction module.

Figure 14 Comparison between price prediction (green) and actual price (yellow) and generation composition in the same period

The model is fairly accurate taking its simplicity into account. The greatest inaccuracies are produced by sudden drops in prices such as those produced by a, relative to overall demand, big production of renewable energy. This depends mostly on wind generation as solar PV is relatively stable in the Spanish summer and thus has easier

patterns to capture. For example if we look at the 07/07 and wind production was high through the day, so prices were kept at a valley and prices did not raise until the night where lack of PV production drew prices upward.

Figure 15 price and generation composition in the same period

To make the model more accurate we would need to first forecast renewable energy sources and take that into account. We could also improve the forecast by forecasting demand first while taking into account the weather. All of this was out of the scope for the goals of the market emulator as the accuracy of the price prediction is not important for the use cases.

4. ASE architecture and API documentation

4.1. Architecture

The ASE is set up as a bundle of docker containers [6] in a single docker-composed file, both docker and the internal containers are either open source or developed by CIRCE. It has the following components:

- Nginx container [7] which acts as a proxy gateway and provides a TSL [8] layer.
- PostgreSQL [9] database container as a historical data repository for the market emulator.
- A Grafana [10] Backoffice to visualize the historical data repository.
- A container with the market emulator module.
- A container with the DSO emulator module.
- A container with overall ASE coordination logic.

The containers for the market emulator module and the DSO emulator module are based on a Python [11] and Flask / Gunicorn [12] [13] (for web server capabilities). Internally we also use several machine learning libraries such as numpy [14], pandas [15], scikit-learn [16] and scikit-multiflow [17].

4.2. API documentation

The ASE has the following external endpoints

GET /pricing	
Description:	Returns pricing data from de market emulator, by default returns pricing for the next 24h

Security:	Requires API token authentication			
Parameters:	date(optional): yyyy-mm-dd hh:mm:ss			
Return example:	<pre>{ "data": { "2022-07-26 11:00:00": 147.81573, "2022-07-26 12:00:00": 148.54176, "2022-07-26 13:00:00": 149.22714, "2022-07-26 14:00:00": 146.58395, "2022-07-26 15:00:00": 143.48302, "2022-07-26 16:00:00": 134.73271, "2022-07-26 17:00:00": 133.84943, "2022-07-26 18:00:00": 136.44283, "2022-07-26 19:00:00": 141.25383, "2022-07-26 20:00:00": 162.51387, "2022-07-26 21:00:00": 175.7483, "2022-07-26 22:00:00": 182.71164, "2022-07-26 23:00:00": 171.15128, "2022-07-27 00:00:00": 146.62608, "2022-07-27 01:00:00": 140.47063, "2022-07-27 02:00:00": 134.59718, "2022-07-27 03:00:00": 133.28577, "2022-07-27 04:00:00": 133.71992, "2022-07-27 05:00:00": 135.50618, "2022-07-27 06:00:00": 140.39417, "2022-07-27 07:00:00": 142.38939, "2022-07-27 08:00:00": 139.7661, "2022-07-27 09:00:00": 134.79291, "2022-07-27 10:00:00": 134.94487, "2022-07-27 11:00:00": 134.82224 }, "reason": "Prediction obtained successfully.", "status": "ok" }</pre>			
GET /drimplicit				
Description:	Returns DSO DR preferences as an implicit DR scheme for a given scenario, by default returns preferences for the next 24h			
Security:	Requires API token authentication			
Parameters	date(optional): yyyy-mm-dd hh:mm:ss			
	scenario: valid values			
	sc0101	sc0376	sc1885	sc0827
	sc844	sc0869	sc1473	sc0000
Return example:	<pre>{ "scenario": "sc0828", "drEventType": "implicit", "startDate": "2022-07-26 10:17:00", "duration": 24, "durationType": "hour", "interval": 1, }</pre>			

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<pre> }] } </pre>											
GET /drexplcit											
Description:	Returns DSO DR preferences as an explicit DR scheme for a given scenario, by default returns preferences for the next 24h										
Security:	Requires API token authentication										
Parameters	date(optional): yyyy-mm-dd hh:mm:ss scenario: valid values <table border="1" data-bbox="598 629 1390 692"> <tr> <td>sc0101</td> <td>sc0376</td> <td>sc1885</td> <td>sc0827</td> <td>sc0828</td> </tr> <tr> <td>sc844</td> <td>sc0869</td> <td>sc1473</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	sc0101	sc0376	sc1885	sc0827	sc0828	sc844	sc0869	sc1473		
sc0101	sc0376	sc1885	sc0827	sc0828							
sc844	sc0869	sc1473									
Return example:	<pre> { "scenario": "sc0828", "drEventType": "explicit", "startDate": "2022-07-26 10:20:59", "duration": 24, "durationType": "hour", "interval": 1, "interval_type": "hour", "signalType": "delta", "signalUnit": "Power", "signals": [{ "value": -1120.0 }, { "value": 1160.0 }, { "value": 462.42324999999998 }, { "value": 644.2423333333333 }, { "value": 644.2423333333333 }, { "value": 462.42324999999998 }, { "value": 462.42324999999998 }, { "value": 462.42324999999998 }, { "value": 462.42324999999998 }] } </pre>										

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5. Assumptions and restrictions

Due to the nature of the project, we don't have data from the actual network for the communities in the project, so we have modelled scenarios with data from Viesgo. Due to this we have created a variety of simulation scenarios with different consumption characteristics. We also have to take into account that the climate of the scenarios is different from the climate of the demo sites which might affect consumption patterns. Another limiting factor of the data is that we don't have data from districts with energy production, so we have had to make a coarse model based on our visual interpretation of data from the Spanish energy market generation composition.

The granularity of the data means it is not suitable for near-real time applications which means we have made a simple model conversion to be able to test real-time applications.

The ASE is not using the flexibility predictions coming for the communities. The plan was to use the flexibility forecast to distribute the explicit DR request among the communities according to their availability, since we only have a single community per network there is no need for this. Anyhow the ASE could easily be further extended and refined/improved to have this functionality if needed.

For the market emulator we have chosen to give price signals using data from the Spanish energy market. There are two reasons for this, the first is that the scenarios we are using are from Spain so it makes sense to use data from the same energy market. The second is that data from the Spanish energy market is freely and readily available for public use. We have made a price prediction module to be able to serve 24 hours of prices at any point in time, however price prediction is not the main functionality of the market emulator, and we are aware that it has room for improvement.

6. Conclusion and next steps

The bulk of development of the ASE is completed, with the possibility of some adjustments on the real-time demand response mode. If at some point, we are going to have multiple communities in the same network we might need some minor modifications to add that.

We can add more scenarios to the model for demonstration of the project. In that sense the DSO emulator module is data driven which means that to add a new scenario we only need to add the corresponding data to the DSO emulator and the code will automatically pick it up.

Another possible improvement would be to have a market emulator use price schemes in line with the country of the pilot site, particularly in cases where we create scenarios based on data from that pilot site /country. However at this point this is considered out of scope for this project.

7. References

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